

2021 University Research Symposium Lightning Round Presentations

Event Description:

Nearly two dozen faculty members engaged in research or scholarship related to Climate Change and Resilience — in disciplines ranging from ecology, economics and engineering to plant biology, psychology and public affairs — took turns showcasing their work in two-minute lightning rounds. The Lightning Round Presentations took place during two sessions on March 23, one in the morning and one in the afternoon.

You can [watch](#) the event in its entirety on the NC State Research YouTube channel.

Moderator: [Laura Kroeger](#), Office of Research and Innovation

Lightning Round Session #1 Presenters

- [Robert Hayes](#), College of Engineering
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)

- [Aranzazu Lascurain](#), Southeast Climate Science Center
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)

- [Rod Rejesus](#), College of Agriculture and Life Sciences
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)

- [Ryan Paerl](#), College of Sciences
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)

- [Jared Rennie](#), North Carolina Institute of Climate Studies
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)

- [Robert Scheller](#), College of Natural Resources
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)

2021 University Research Symposium Lightning Round Presentations

- [Corey Davis](#), North Carolina State Climate Office
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)
 - [Sonja Salmon](#), Wilson College of Textiles
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)
 - [Jordan Kern](#), College of Natural Resources
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)
 - [William Hoffmann](#), College of Sciences
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)
 - [Marcelo Ardon Sayao](#), College of Natural Resources
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)
 - [Shevaun Neupert](#), College of Humanities and Social Sciences
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)
-

Lightning Round Session #2 Presenters

- [Jared Bowden](#), College of Natural Resources
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)
- [Rebecca Ward](#), North Carolina State Climate Office
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)

2021 University Research Symposium Lightning Round Presentations

- [Christopher Galik](#), College of Humanities and Social Sciences
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)
- [Gary Lackmann](#), College of Sciences
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)
- [Astrid Schnetzer](#), College of Sciences
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)
- [Chris Osburn](#), College of Sciences
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)
- [Jacob Eapen](#), College of Engineering
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)
- [Shiyan Jiang](#), College of Education
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)
- [Gavin Smith](#), College of Design
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)
- [Lada Kochtcheeva](#), College of Humanities and Social Sciences
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)
- [Phil Westmoreland](#), College of Engineering
 - [View Slides](#)
 - [View Video](#)